

Understanding and Navigating Power Dynamics Workbook

A guide for claiming your power for
systems transformation

Authors: B. Malaika Rumala, Monique Price, Regina Cannon

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Authors

B Malaika Rumala

Monique Price

Regina Cannon

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Cover Art - Explained

"These systems are built on a cracked foundation of historical inequities leading to present-day outcomes. All systems need solutions from the power of people with lived experiences to correct the multisystemic inequities ranging from the housing system and beyond. This means dismantling and uprooting inequitable systemic processes, policies, and practices since inequities in processes, policies, and practices lead to inequities in outcomes. People with lived experience have a strong powerful leadership role for sustainable, equitable, transparent, and accountable outcomes when meaningfully and authentically engaged as decision-makers"

- B. Malaika Rumala

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Topics

On this journey to claim your power, the following topics will be explored with accompanying activities, tools, and resources:

- Power Dynamics defined
- Power of People with Lived Experience
- Power of Systems
- Power of Data
- Power of Language
- Power of Making Good Trouble
- Power of Navigating Tokenism
- Power of the Arts
- Power of Funding
- Power of understanding the historical roots to inform changes for the present and future
- Power of Expanding the Bench

Understanding Power Dynamics

Understanding Power Dynamics

- To claim your power, it is important for people with lived experience to understand power dynamics for naming, framing, and knowing what one is claiming.

Power Dynamics

Power dynamics are the ways in which power is distributed and exercised within relationships, groups, or societies.

Power dynamics involves understanding who holds influence, authority, or control in various situations, and how this can impact decision-making, resource distribution, and opportunities.

Power dynamics impacts who is included in the decision making process

Activity

Reflect on ways you would like to claim your power.

Power of People with Lived Experience

People with Lived Experience

- People with Lived Experience have knowledge of a system, process, or issue from the perspective of those affected by, or trying to engage with that resource
- People with Lived Experience play an integral role in helping organizations relate to communities.
- People with Lived Experience are needed to improve results within organizations and systems.
- People with Lived Experience have a personal understanding of the inequities and solutions to bridge inequities in a system.

People with Lived Experience (continued):

- People with Lived Experience have knowledge of a system, process, or issue from the perspective of being directly impacted.
- People with lived experience are the source of solutions for needed changes having been directly impacted.

Activity

- Are you a person with lived experience?
- Write down your lived experience and systems that you have been impacted by.
- Based on your lived experiences, write down solutions that you have to make things better.

Tool

Assessment tool to engage People with Lived Experience

Assessment Areas	Yes	No
I know how to engage People with Lived Experience authentically		
I have members on my team with lived experience in focus areas		
I have enabled people with lived experience to co-design in focus areas		
I view listening sessions with people with lived experience as an important part of engagement		
Addressing equity in collaboration with people with lived experience is important for the work that I do		
People with lived experience have decision-making roles in this collaboration		
People with lived experience are equal partners in this initiative with no hierarchies		
I feel it is important to share transparent information directly with people with lived experience as equal partners		
I involve people with lived experience in drafting grants		
I involve people with lived experience in drafting budgets		
I involve people with lived experience with an opportunity to provide input on the agenda before meetings		
I provide people with lived experience opportunities for upward mobility		
I provide people with lived experience opportunities to expand in different areas beyond existing roles or title		
Similar to many professions, a person with lived experience has expertise. I understand that this expertise is highly valued and therefore people with lived experience should be fairly compensated for the value of expertise.		

Source: The above tool is adapted and modified from Rumala B. et al. (2020) Assessment tool for engaging people with lived experience. People with Lived Experience Institute

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Resources

- Definition - People with Lived Experience
- People with Lived Experience Institute

<https://www.pleinstitute.org/>

- Song - People with Lived Experience as
the Source of Solutions:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zIB2ZLW>

[NF74](#)

Power of Systems

Source: Rumala B. *Interconnected Systems Impacting Equity* (2021). People with Lived Experience Institute.

Power of Systems

- To understand navigating power dynamics, it is important to first understand the complex systems one operates in.
- For example, what does it mean to address systemic issues?
- Systems is more than a word; a system consists of multiple layers.

Source: Art Concept Design by B Malaika Rumala (2024) called Systems on Cracked Foundation needs People with Lived Experience to inform solutions

- A system consists of both the tangible and intangible.
- The tangible and intangible includes people, resources, services, relationships, values, and perceptions.
- These elements impact equitable outcomes for people with lived experience.
- Therefore, systems transformation is about intentionally addressing the root causes of problems through dismantling and uprooting the inequities.
- A bandage cannot be put on a broken foundation that is built on centuries of

systemic historical inequities including but not limited to systemic racism.

- A bandage approach is not sustainable and leads to further inequities.
- Therefore, sustainable solutions must focus on uprooting root causes for a healthy stable foundation.

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Activity

Tool

Claiming your power starts first with understanding, naming, and framing the systemic inequities experienced

Name the system you are impacted by	Name the elements of the system you are impacted by (people, resources, values, perceptions, services)	Name the inequities you have experienced	Name the solutions that you have

Source: The above tool is adapted and modified from Rumala B. (2023) Assessment tool for understanding, naming, framing, and solutions for inequities experienced in systems. People with Lived Experience Institute

Power of Data

Power of Data

- Data is a powerful tool when used correctly.
- When misused, data can further isolate, marginalize, and perpetuate oppression for People with Lived Experience.
- The BIG Question, is all data factual? Does data tell the whole story?

If you are familiar with the nursery rhyme "Liar, Liar pants on fire". You are correct. The answer is No. The data reveals the intent of the data collector based on what was asked. This means the true holistic story is limited based on the questions that were asked yielding answers that might be narrowly focused and may not reveal the totality of what is happening. Unfortunately,

data can also be manipulated to provide a false narrative.

- Therefore, the role of people with lived experience is to interrogate systems and this includes the data produced by systems. Interrogating systems help people with lived experience claim their power in the data narrative.

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Tool for interrogating data

Question Areas for Interrogation	Answers
Who developed the collection tool for the data?	
Were people with lived experience involved in formulating the data collection tool?	
Did people with lived experience have input in refining the data collection tool?	
Who benefits from the data collection?	
Were both qualitative and quantitative methods used to gather the whole story?	
What is missing from the data?	
Who is missing from the data?	
Does the data inform actionable solutions to benefit people with lived experience?	
Does the data inform actionable solutions to inform equity?	
Is there accountability in the data collected for people with lived experience?	
Is there transparency in the data for people with lived experience?	
Who is funding this data collection effort?	
Are there conflicts of interest negatively impacting people with lived experience?	
Does what is collected treat people with lived experience with dignity?	
Does the data collected support the next steps for people with lived experience thriving?	
Have the data results been shared with people with lived experience for input?	

Source: Modified and Adapted from Rumala B (2022) Let's keep it real: Role of People with Lived Experience in interrogating data. People with Lived Experience Institute.

Power of Data

Activity

- Reflect on systems people with lived experience should be involved in to interrogate for data and other areas to improve accountability, transparency, and responsibility.
- What are current inequitable processes, policies, and practices for data you will change to move the needle toward equity for People with Lived Experience?

Power of Language

Power of Language

- Language has been used to further propagate inequities across systems. The power of language has a generational impact in defining which populations thrive and which populations remain oppressed based on processes, policies, and practices.
- Within the housing system, significant impacts of language continue to cause generational disparities and lack of access due to systemic racism including but not limited to:
 - Redlining in which government officials in the system marked maps with red lines in black neighborhoods to stop investment due to what the government

- officials labeled as risky investments due to the black population.
- Home Owners' Loan Corporation labeling predominantly black neighborhoods as risky or hazardous on maps leading to denial of home loans.
 - Predominantly black neighborhoods being labeled as undesirable compared to predominantly white neighborhoods being labeled as desirable.
 - Language on racial-ethnic make-up of neighborhood impacting credit for mortgage lending. This adversely impacted minority neighborhoods.
 - Zoning language with exclusionary practices such as single-family housing to prevent affordable multi-family housing.

- Property deeds that contained covenant restrictions to prevent majority black and non-white buyers from purchasing homes.

The historical racism embedded in language continues and has deeply impacted generational wealth due to a lack of home ownership.

- This workbook also highlights a present-day language of “resilience” that has propagated through systems causing further inequities.
- The inequities are highlighted in this short animation film called: lived experience of the inequities of the Resilience Model. A system interrogative

and critical lens is applied in addressing this in both the short animation film and published scholarly paper. While resilience is not a bad word, in this context the language of resilience masks, suppresses, and overshadows addressing the root causes leading people with lived experience to become more resilient against inequities.

Source: B. Malaika Rumala, Lived experience of the inequities of the Resilience model (2021). <https://youtu.be/S-jUKPiG7IE>

Activity

- Name language that has negatively impacted people with lived experience that needs to be changed.
- What are your solutions for changing the language for the benefit of people with lived experience?

Resources

Scholarly Paper: Rumala B. (2021). Rethinking the resilience model in the context of Inequities. *Journal of the People with Lived Experience Institute*, 1(1), 4-6.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4995839>

Power of Making Good Trouble

Power of Making Good Trouble

Good Trouble is a term coined by Representative John Lewis

Source: Google images

- As a person with lived experience change the narrative and step into the power of causing good trouble. You are not a troublemaker; you are causing good trouble to dismantle the systemic inequities.

- Regina Cannon, CEO, ARC4Justice, highlights Good trouble and emphasizes that:
 - Good trouble is necessary to ensure people with lived experience are benefiting.
 - We need to be comfortable with calling out unjust things in boldness. This may include shutting down meetings where people with lived experience are not represented.
 - There are necessary consequences that occur for making Good Trouble.
 - One person with lived experience should not be the only one making good trouble,

it is important to kick the door open for other people with lived experience to join.

- Regina Cannon, CEO, ARC4Justice, emphasizes the need to “take the door off the hinges” so that people with lived experience are not stopped from entering due to systemic racism and other inequities.
- She also emphasizes the need to transition from being Racial Equity advocates to being racial equity brokers because this is where the power resides for People with Lived Experience.
- Advocacy brings awareness and brokering requires brokering of power

to enable changes in policies, laws and direct action.

- Regina Cannon, CEO, ARC4Justice emphasizes that People with lived experience should see themselves as a racial equity broker to negotiate their power back.

Activity

- What are some of the ways you have gotten into some *Good Trouble*?
- How can you be a racial equity broker to take your power back?

Power of Navigating Tokenism

Power of Navigating Tokenism

Source: Google images, definition from Arthur Chan

Tokenism + Fake inclusion +
Check box approach =
Limited to NO Power

"Often times it is black women who are tokenized in spaces. We can use our power to flex, call out the behavior of being tokenized, and mention the changes that need to be made" - Taura Brown, ARC4Justice Expanding The Bench Leadership Academy

Activity

Have you felt tokenized and how did you navigate to claim your power?

Power of the Arts

Power of the Arts

- The arts are a powerful mechanism for people with lived experience to claim power, mobilize, and dismantle systemic inequities.
- People with lived experience tapping into all gifts and talents is needed due to the pervasiveness of systemic inequities.
- The arts enable another form of communication and messaging for the authentic voice of people with lived experiences who are often silenced or muted to inform systems change,
- As a person with lived experience whose voice was marginalized and silenced, the author of the resources highlighted

below started to integrate gifts and talents in the arts as a tool for authentically and transparently sharing without filtering of voice.

- The arts provided an opportunity to address the inequities and claim power.
- There is a severe underrepresentation of short animation filmmakers in this space but it presents an opportunity for people with lived experience narratives to come across loud and clear, and to receive funding without compromising core values.
- Below, the examples of the author's work in The Arts are highlighted in the areas of short animation film, spoken word, song, and visual arts as an avenue for

social justice across interconnected systems.

The Arts genre - Short Animation Film:

A Seat at the decision-making table by B. Malaika Rumala (2024)

Link: <https://youtu.be/iv1QC2r8xW8>

The Arts genre - Short Animation Film (cont'd):

Inequities of the Resilience model by B
Malaika Rumala (2021) Link:

<https://youtu.be/S-jUkPiG7IE>

The Arts Genre - Spoken word and poetry

- Spoken Word - Vultures at the perimeter....Office Cell by B Malaika Rumala (2022) - Written during oppression
- Spoken Word - Rising Beyond by B Malaika Rumala (2022) - Written after being empowered

Lived Experience Spoken Word Poetry in Motion: Understanding Power, Addressing Power and Creating Change

Part 1

Vultures at the perimeter....Office cell
By Dr. B. Malaika Rumala (2022)

Suited prison guards on the perimeter
Circle the center
Like Vultures leaning for the kill
Watching every word
Watching every movement
Internally attacking
No understanding
Replication of oppression
Acts and plastered smile on faces
Falsely labeled as microaggressions
Beneath the mask, the truth lay bare
Microaggressions, be it not
Ignorance, be it not
It is Racism
Justifying systemic inequities
Justifying systemic racism
through policies untold
Creating invisibility
Footsteps back and forth
Listening to every chatter
Valued externally but internally oppressed by others
From suited prison guards at the perimeter
Watching the center like Vultures leaning for the kill

Part 2

Rising Beyond by Dr. B. Malaika Rumala (2022)

From the deep trenches
A colorful Phoenix
rising from the ashes of Vulture oppression
As suited prison guards lurk
The village speaks
The tribe speaks of right to live
To live with dignity and thrive
Of necessary transformation
Weaponized policy transformed to healing
Hidden voices emerge
In unity, beneath the mask
Stripping plastered smiles
Acts founded on truth
By those most impacted
To dismantle inequities
Building bridges of change
From equity to thriving
Rising Beyond

See yourself impacting systems

The Arts Genre - Spoken word and poetry cont'd

Activity

Following the themes below mentioned in B. Malaika Rumala's 2022 spoken word poem "Rising Beyond", In your role, how can you address power for yourself and power for others in the spoken word poem:

- "The village speak?"
- "Hidden voices emerge?"
- "Weaponized policy be transformed into healing?"
- "You build bridges of change"
- "Have acts founded on truth"
- "You dismantle inequities"

The Arts Genre - Song

Deeper than hair by B Malaika Rumala (2020)
Emphasizes systemic racism

Link - <https://youtu.be/IPvYR4d25Mw>

The Arts Genre - Song cont'd

Song - People with lived experience Source of Solutions by B Malaika Rumala (2020)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z1B2ZLWNF74>

The Arts genre - Visual/Imagery

Visual/Imagery art by B Malaika Rumala (2020) - showing social justice, hair and afro pick comb

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The Arts

Activity

- Name your gifts and talents that you can use as a person with lived experience to claim your power.
- In what areas would you like to use your gifts and talents?

Power of Funding

Power of Funding

- Power dynamics and funding are mutually intertwined.
- The importance cannot be underestimated since funding can promote or block the progress of dismantling historic and present-day inequities for people with lived experience.
- Historical and present-day inequities within the funding ecosystem include but are not limited to:
 - A lack of engaging people with lived experience as true decision-makers for funding.

- Inequitable request for proposals to authentically engage people with lived experience starting from the grassroots levels.
- Inequitable criteria and standards for evaluating proposals that are exclusionary for people with lived experience.
- A funding ecosystem of inner circle vetting that provides grants to the same actors and does not expand the bench for new voices with solutions that work for sustainable solutions for people with lived experience impacted by inequities.

- Embedded policies and practices in the funding that have become normalized without accountability.
- A lack of mechanisms for unrestricted funding for people with lived experience at the grassroots level and beyond.
- Tokenized approach by some organizations seeking to fulfill Request For Proposals (RFP) and approaching impacted people with lived experience as an after-thought with limited authentic engagement.

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Power of Funding

People with lived experience can claim power through this interrogation tool below for the funding ecosystem. This funding tool also serves as a base for action next steps for funding organizations to address processes for engaging impacted people with lived experience.

Tool for interrogating the funding ecosystem

Questions for interrogation	Answers	Action next steps for the Funding Ecosystem
Are impacted people with lived experience involved in the drafting of the request for proposals?		
Are impacted people with lived experience involved in drafting the evaluation criteria?		
Are impacted people with lived experience involved in the review of the grant proposals?		
Are impacted people with lived experience involved in keeping organizations that		

receive funds accountable for treating people with lived experience with dignity?		
Are impacted people with live experience involved in audits to keep organizations accountable for fairly compensating people with lived experience for the funds received?		
Has there been engagement of grassroots impacted people with lived experience to have access to applying for funding?		
Are there mechanisms for impacted people with lived experience to receive unrestricted funding?		
Have mechanisms been included to expand the table for new and unheard voices in the funding ecosystem?		

Source: Modified and Adapted from Rumala B (2023) A Tool for People with lived experience to interrogate the funding ecosystem

Power of understanding the historical roots to inform changes for the present and future

Power of understanding the historical roots to inform changes for the present and future

- Understanding the historical roots leading to present-day inequities that have impacted generations of people with lived experience is the key to providing solutions that are sustainable.
- The history of many of the inequities seen today for impacted people with lived experience is built on a foundation of systemic racism.
- Understanding the roots, helps solutions to be informed from a dismantling and uprooting approach rather than a bandage approach of “fixing the system”.

- The system is designed to do exactly as intended due to the inequitable foundation upon which it was built. Therefore, addressing through solutions requires addressing the foundational inequitable roots.
- The foundational roots can only be addressed by understanding the history.
- Arc4Justice discusses the historical roots leading to present-day inequities and all are encouraged to delve deep into understanding.

Activity

- Read and engage with the resources available on the ARC4Justice website
- How do historical inequities impact present-day inequities for people with lived experience?

Resources

ARC4Justice website

<https://arc4justice.org/> Anti-Racism
Center for Justice and Transformative
Change

Power of Expanding the Bench

Power of Expanding the Bench

In this guidebook for understanding and navigating power dynamics to claim your power to transform systems, we have explored several topics including Power Dynamics, Power of People with Lived Experience, Power of Systems, Power of Data, Power of Language, Power of Making Good Trouble, Power of Navigating Tokenism, Power of the Arts, Power of Funding, Power of knowing the historical roots to inform changes for the present and future, and last but not least, we explore Power of Expanding The Bench in this section.

- You have an important role in expanding the bench, and opening the doors for impacted people with lived experience.

- Expanding the bench means that you do not yield to the status quo that has become normalized.
- Through expanding the bench your guide is justice-centered, equity-focused, anti-racism-centered, and uplifts the voices of impacted people with lived experience

Power of Expanding the Bench

Activity

In each of the areas explored on the journey through this guide, list the actions you will take for expanding the bench.

Guide Topic Areas	Actions I will take to Expand the Bench
Power Dynamics	
Power of People with Lived Experience	
Power of Systems	
Power of Data	
Power of Language	
Power of Making Good Trouble	
Power of Navigating Tokenism	
Power of the Arts	
Power of Funding	
Power of understanding the historical roots to inform changes for the present and future	
Power of Expanding the bench	

Anti-Racism Center for Justice and Transformative Change